

INFLUENCE OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS ON THE STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF S.M.C.

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ABSTRACT

The S.M.C. is used nowadays in a wide range of applications taking the place of other kinds of materials, specially the metallic ones. The processing parameters during the transformation of this material can affect its properties.

In this report the influence of some parameters as temperature, processing pressure and curing time are studied, comparing them with the structure and mechanical properties to low and high temperature of some S.M.C.

INTRODUCTION

The S.M.C. products are getting into very different kinds of markets, due to the joint of good mechanical properties, low weight and competitive price. In different industries automative, electric etc., the S.M.C. pieces are supporting tensions at different temperatures.

A good deal of papers have been published studying both mechanical properties of these materials and gathering the processing techniques. But there is little literature both fields processing with morphology and mechanical properties./1/, /2/,/3/.

In this research work we intend to study the effect that processing and its different parameters have on the structure, morphology and mechanical properties on the material.

The ultimate aim of this project is to obtain some relationships between the mechanical behaviour of the material and the processing parameters used. This way it shall be possible to optimize the processing cycle for obtaining a material with some specific properties.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The S.M.C. employed during this work was a 35% ortophtalic polyester with 25% fibre glass and 40% aluminium hydrate.

Pressing of the S.M.C. was performed in a 100 T press, with variable values for the pressure cycles, temperature and curing time. The pressing pressure was measured through the force developed by the press, while the temperature was measured with thermocouples sitted in each part of the mold and the curing time was considered as the total holding time of the pressure in the cycle. Two of the parameters have been fixed changing the third one, obtaining by this mean a

complete spectrum of conditions between 2 and 7 minutes of curing time, 130° and 170° of processing temperature and pressure between 2 and 10 MPa.

After the process, the structure of the material has been characterized. The conditions of the resin have been studied with Tg measurements using dilatometric techniques. The flowing behaviour of the material so as the fibre orientation and size distribution have been studied by means of optic and electronic microscopy. Before the observation of the specimens using the scanning electron microscopy, the metalization of those specimens is necessary.

The next step was the study of the mechanical properties of the specimens. The material has been loaded in tension. The mechanical test were carried in an INSTRON 6025 machine. Three values were studied: failure strength, elastic modulus and ultimate strain. The specimens were conditioned at 24°C and 50 percent relative humidity for a minimum of 48h before testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of the process parameters over the mechanical properties may be observed in Fig. 1-9.

The influence of the mold temperature over tensile properties (max. strength, modulus and strain percentage) is displayed in Fig 1-3. As the mold temperature increases a slight rise in both the tensile strength and the modulus may be observed. Such increase may be due to a faster curing at higher mold temperatures. This is also corroborated by the increment of the Tg as the mold temperature increases. The strain decreases as the mold temperature increases.

The influence of the cure time on the tensile properties may be observed in Fig 4 to 6. The tensile strength shows that maximum is obtained at a curing time of 2.5 minutes. Tensile strength decreases with lower curing times probably due to the fact that the material is undercured. When curing times exceed 2.5 minutes a diminution of the curing time is observed due perhaps to the overcured resin phase of the composite. Similar examples are shown in the bibliographic references./4/.

The same behaviour over the tensile strength may be observed concerning the modulus. However no clear effect may be appreciated for the elongation at break.

Fig. 7-9 represent the influence of the mold pressure on tensile properties. When mold pressure increases a remarkable increase of tensile strength is also experimented. At the same time there is also an enhancement of the tensile modulus. This effect of strength increasing with pressure might be due to a diminution of voids. Such diminution results in a better adherence between the fibre and the matrix improving therefore the mechanical properties. The effect of the mold pressure over the elongation percentage is small and insignificant.

In Fig. 10 and 11 the influence of both the time curing and the temperature of the mold on the Tg of the material is displayed. In both cases the Tg increases as a result of the curing rate growth of the material.

Fig.1 Effect of mold temperature on tensile strength (Mold pressure 4 MPa and cure time 3 min.)

Fig.2 Effect of mold temperature on tensile modulus (Mold pressure 4 MPa and cure time 3 min.)

Fig.3 Effect of mold temperature on tensile strain (mold pressure 4 MPa and cure time 3 min.)

Fig.4 Effect of cure time on tensile strength (Mold temperature 150 °C and mold pressure 4 MPa)

Fig.5 Effect of cure time on tensile modulus (Mold temperature 150 °C and mold pressure 4 MPa)

Fig.6 Effect of cure time on tensile strain (Mold temperature 150 °C and mold pressure 4 MPa)

Fig.7 Effect of mold pressure on tensile strength (Mold temperature 130 °C and cure time 3 min.)

Fig.8 Effect of mold pressure on tensile modulus (Mold temperature 130 °C and cure time 3 min.)

Fig.9 Effect of mold pressure on tensile strain (Mold temperature 130 °C and cure time 3 min.)

Fig. 10 Effect of mold temperature on TG of S.M.C.

Fig. 11 Effect of cure time on TG of S.M.C.

The influence of the processing parameters on the tensile properties is similar to what has been observed in the flexural properties studied in preceding works./5/.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of the processing parameters on the mechanical properties and on the morphology of an S.M.C. has been studied. The tensile properties and the Tg of the material were studied through dilatometry measurements. In both cases it was possible to observe that curing time and mold pressure and temperature have an important effect over the properties of the S.M.C. Besides, results obtained may be used for optimizing the cure cycle of this material.

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